

Some Properties of a h-Randers Finsler Space

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Abstract: The purpose of the present paper is to obtain the relation between imbedding class numbers of tangent Riemannian spaces to (M^n, L) and (M^n, L^*) where $L^*(x, y)$ is obtained from the transformation of $L(x, y)$ is given by

$$L^*(x, y) \rightarrow L(x, y) + b_i(x, y)y^i$$

Key Words: Riemannian metric, h-vector, imbedding class.

AMS(2010): 53B40, 53C60.

§1. Introduction

In 1971 Matsumoto [5] introduced the transformation of Finsler metric

$$\bar{L}(x, y) \rightarrow L(x, y) + b_i y^i \quad (1.1)$$

and obtain the relation between the imbedding class numbers of a tangent Riemannian spaces to (M^n, L) and a Finsler space (M^n, \bar{L}) which is obtained by the transformation of the Finsler metric L by the relation given by in the equation (1.1). Since a concurrent vector field is a function of (x) i.e., position only, assuming $b_i(x)$ as a concurrent vector field, Matsumoto [6] studied the R3-likeness of Finsler spaces (M^n, L) and (M^n, \bar{L}) . Singh and Prasad [14,11] generalized the concept of concurrent vector field and introduced the semi-parallel and concircular vector fields which are functions of (x) only. Assuming $b_i(x)$ as a concircular vector field, Prasad, Singh and Singh [11] studied the R3-likeness of (M^n, L) and (M^n, \bar{L}) .

If $L(x, y)$ is a metric function of Riemannian space then $\bar{L}(x, y)$ reduces to the metric function of Rander's space. Such a Finsler metric was first introduced by G. Randers [13] from the standpoint of general theory of relativity and applied to the theory of the electron microscope by R. S. Ingarden [3] who first named it as Randers space. The geometrical properties of this space have been studied by various workers [2, 7, 9, 12, 15]. In 1970 Numata [10] has studied the properties of (M^n, \bar{L}) which is obtained from Minkowski space (M^n, L) by transformation

¹Received August 18, 2016, Accepted February 21, 2017.

(1.1). In all those works the function $b_i(x)$ are assumed to be functions of (x) only.

In 1980, Izumi [4] while studying the conformal transformation of Finsler spaces, introduced the h-vector b_i which is v-covariantly constant with respect to Cartan's connection CT and satisfies the relation

$$LC_{ij}^h b_h = \rho h_{ij}$$

Thus the h-vector b_i is not only a function of (x) but it is also a function of directional arguments satisfying $L\dot{\partial}_j b_i = \rho h_{ij}$. The purpose of the present paper is to obtain the relation between imbedding class numbers of tangent Riemannian spaces to (M^n, L) and (M^n, L^*) where $L^*(x, y)$ is obtained from the transformation of $L(x, y)$ is given by

$$L^*(x, y) \rightarrow L(x, y) + \beta(x, y), \quad (1.2)$$

where $\beta(x, y) = b_i(x, y)y^i$, i.e. $b_i(x, y)$ is the function of position and direction both.

§2. An h-Vector in (M^n, L)

Let b_i be a vector field in the Finsler space (M^n, L) . If $b_i(x, y)$ satisfies the conditions

$$b_i|_j = 0, \quad (2.1)$$

$$LC_{ij}^h b_h = \rho h_{ij}, \quad (2.2)$$

then the vector field b_i is called an h-vector [4]. Here $|_i$ denotes the v-covariant derivative with respect to y^i in the case of Cartan's connection CT , C_{ij}^h is the cartan's C-tensor, h_{ij} is the angular metric tensor and ρ is given by

$$\rho = \frac{LC^i b_i}{(n-1)}, \quad (2.3)$$

where C^i is the torsion tensor given by $C_{jk}^i g^{jk}$.

Lemma 2.1([4]) *If b_i is an h-vector then the function ρ and are independent of y .*

Since The v-covariant derivation of $b^2 = g^{ij}b_i b_j$ and the fact that g^{ij} is v-covariantly constant yield

$$b\dot{\partial}_k b = g^{ij}b_i b_j|_k.$$

In the view of (2.1) we have

$$\dot{\partial}_k b = 0.$$

Thus we have

Lemma 2.2 *The magnitude b of an h-vector is independent of y .*

From (2.1), Ricci identity [8] and the fact that $S_{ihjk} = g_{hr}S_{ijk}^r$ is skew-symmetric in h and

i we have

$$b_i|_j|_k - b_i|_k|_j = -S_{ijk}^h b_h = 0.$$

Thus we have

Lemma 2.3 For an h -vector b_i we have $S_{hijk} b^h = 0$, where S_{hijk} are components of v -curvature tensor of Cartan's connection CT .

The concept of concurrent vector field in (M^n, L) has been introduced by Tachibana [16] and its properties have been studied by Matsumoto [6]. A vector field b_i in (M^n, L) is said to be concurrent if it satisfies the condition (2.1) and

$$b_i|_j = -g_{ij}, \quad (2.4)$$

where $|_j$ denotes h -covariant differentiation with respect to x^i in the sense of Cartan's connection CT .

Applying Ricci Identity [8]

$$b_i|_j|_k - b_i|_k|_j = -b_h P_{ijk}^h - b_i|_h C_{jk}^h - b_i|_h P_{jk}^h$$

and using (2.1) and (2.4) we have

$$P_{ijk}^h b_h + C_{ijk} = 0.$$

Since $P_{imjk} = g_{mh} P_{ijk}^h$ is skew-symmetric in i and m , contraction of above equation with $b^i = g^{ij} b_j$ gives $C_{ijk} b^i = 0$. Hence we have the following

Lemma 2.4 An h -vector b_i with $\rho \neq 0$ is not a concurrent vector field.

§3. Properties of the h -Randers Finsler Space

Let b_i be an h -vector in the Finsler space (M^n, L) and (M^n, L^*) be another Finsler space whose fundamental function $L^*(x, y)$ is given by (1.2).

Since b_i is an h -vector, from (2.1) and (2.2), we get

$$\dot{\partial}_j b_i = L^{-1} \rho h_{ij}, \quad (3.1)$$

which after using the indicatory property of h_{ij} yields $\dot{\partial}_j \beta = b_j$.

Definition 3.1 Let M^n be an n -dimensional differentiable manifold and F^n be a Finsler space equipped with a fundamental function $L(x, y)$, $(y^i = \dot{x}^i)$ of M^n . A change in the fundamental function L by the equation (1.2) on the same manifold M^n is called h -Randers change. A space equipped with fundamental metric L^* is called h -Randers changed Finsler space F^{*n} .

Now differentiating (1.2) with respect to y^i we have

$$l_i^* = l_i + b_i, \quad (3.2)$$

where $l_i = \dot{\partial}_i L$ is the normalized supporting element in (M^n, L) and $l_i^* = \dot{\partial}_i L^*$ is the normalized element of support in (M^n, L^*) . The quantities of (M^n, L^*) will be denoted by starred letter. Now differentiating (3.2) with respect to y^j then the angular metric tensor $h_{ij}^* = \dot{\partial}_j l_i^*$ is given by

$$h_{ij}^* = \sigma h_{ij}, \quad (3.3)$$

where $\sigma = LL^{-1}(1 + \rho)$. Hence we have

$$g_{ij}^* = \sigma g_{ij} + (1 - \sigma)l_i l_j + (l_i b_j + l_j b_i) + b_i b_j. \quad (3.4)$$

From (3.4) the relation between the contravariant components of the fundamental tensors can be derived as follows

$$g^{*ij} = \sigma^{-1}g^{ij} - (1 + \rho^2)\sigma^{-3}(1 - b^2 - \sigma)l^i l^j - (1 + \rho)\sigma^{-2}(l^i b^j + l^j b^i), \quad (3.5)$$

where b is the magnitude of the vector b_i .

From the lemma (2.1) and (3.2) we have

$$\dot{\partial}_i \sigma = \frac{(1 + \rho)}{L} m_i, \quad (3.6)$$

$$m_i = b_i - \frac{\beta}{L} l_i. \quad (3.7)$$

Now differentiating (3.3) with respect to y^k (3.2), (3.6), (3.3) and the fact

$$\dot{\partial}_k h_{ij} = 2C_{ijk} - L^{-1}(h_{ik} l_j + h_{jk} l_i),$$

we have

$$C_{ijk}^* = \sigma C_{ijk} + (1 + \rho) \frac{h_{ij} m_k + h_{jk} m_i + h_{ki} m_j}{2L}. \quad (3.8)$$

From the definition of m_i , it is evident that

$$\begin{aligned} (a) \quad m_i l^i, & \quad (b) \quad m_i b^i = b^2 - \frac{\beta^2}{L^2} = m^i m_i, \\ (c) \quad h_{ij} m^i = h_{ij} b^i = m_j, & \quad (d) \quad C_{ij}^h m_h = L^{-1} \rho h_{ij}. \end{aligned} \quad (3.9)$$

From (2.1), (3.5), (3.8) and (3.9) we have

$$\begin{aligned} C_{ij}^{*r} &= C_{ij}^r + \frac{(h_{ij} m^r + h_j^r m_i + h_i^r m_j)}{2L^*} - \frac{1}{L^*} \{ \rho \\ &+ \frac{L}{2L^*} (b^2 - \frac{\beta^2}{L^2}) \} h_{ij} + \frac{L}{L^*} m_i m_j \} l^r. \end{aligned} \quad (3.10)$$

Proposition 3.1 Let $F^{*n} = (M^n, L^*)$ be an n -dimensional Finsler space obtained from the h -Randers change of the Finsler space $F^n = (M^n, L)$, then the normalized supporting element l_i^* , angular metric tensor h_{ij}^* , fundamental metric tensor g_{ij}^* and $(h)hv$ -torsion tensor C_{ijk}^* of F^{*n} are given by (3.2), (3.3), (3.4) and (3.8) respectively.

Proposition 3.2 Let $F^{*n} = (M^n, L^*)$ be an n -dimensional Finsler space obtained from the h -Randers change of the Finsler space $F^n = (M^n, L)$, then the reciprocal of the fundamental metric tensor g_{ij}^* is given by (3.5).

The curvature tensor S_{hijk} of (M^n, L^*) is given by

$$S_{hijk}^* = C_{hkm}^* C_{ij}^{*m} - C_{hjm}^* C_{ik}^{*m}. \quad (3.11)$$

From the equation (3.8) and (3.10), we have

$$\begin{aligned} C_{hkm}^* C_{ij}^{*m} &= \sigma C_{hkm} C_{ij}^m + \alpha h_{ij} h_{hk} + \frac{(1+\rho)}{2L} \{C_{ijk} m_h + C_{hjk} m_i \\ &\quad + C_{hik} m_j + C_{hij} m_k\} + \frac{(1+\rho)}{4LL^*} \{2h_{ij} m_k m_h \\ &\quad + 2h_{hk} m_i m_j + h_{ik} m_j m_h + h_{ih} m_j m_k + h_{jk} m_i m_h \\ &\quad + h_{jh} m_i m_k\}, \end{aligned} \quad (3.12)$$

where $\alpha = \frac{(1+\rho)\rho}{4L^2} + \frac{1+\rho}{4LL^*} (b^2 - \frac{\beta^2}{L^2})$. Thus from (3.11) we have

$$S_{hijk}^* = \sigma S_{hijk} + h_{ij} d_{hk} + h_{hk} d_{ij} - h_{ik} d_{jh} - h_{hj} d_{ik}, \quad (3.13)$$

where $d_{ij} = \frac{\sigma}{2} h_{ij} + \frac{1+\rho}{4LL^*} m_i m_j$.

If we define the tensor A_{ij} and B_{ij} as

$$A_{ij} = \frac{h_{ij} + d_{ij}}{\sqrt{2}}, \quad B_{ij} = \frac{h_{ij} - d_{ij}}{\sqrt{2}}, \quad (3.14)$$

then S_{hijk}^* is written as

$$S_{hijk}^* = \sigma S_{hijk} - (A_{hj} A_{ik} - A_{hk} A_{ij}) + (B_{hj} B_{ik} - B_{hk} B_{ij}). \quad (3.15)$$

Thus we have

Proposition 3.3 Let $F^{*n} = (M^n, L^*)$ be an n -dimensional Finsler space obtained from the h -Randers change of the Finsler space $F^n = (M^n, L)$, then the curvature tensor S_{hijk}^* is given by (3.15).

If $|_j$ denotes v-covariant differentiation with respect to y^j in (M^n, L^*) then we have

$$h_{ij}|_k - h_{ik}|_j = \frac{(h_{ij} l_k - h_{ik} l_j)}{L}, \quad (3.16)$$

$$m_i|_j - m_j|_i = \frac{(m_i l_j - m_j l_i)}{L}, \quad (3.17)$$

$$d_{ij}|_k - d_{ik}|_j = \frac{(d_{ij} l_k - d_{ik} l_j)}{L}. \quad (3.18)$$

Hence from (3.14), (3.16) and (3.18), we get

$$A_{ij}|_k - A_{ik}|_j = \frac{(B_{ij} l_k - B_{ik} l_j)}{L}, \quad (3.19)$$

$$B_{ij}|_k - B_{ik}|_j = \frac{(A_{ij} l_k - A_{ik} l_j)}{L}. \quad (3.20)$$

§4. Imbedding Class Numbers of Tangent Riemannian Space to (M^n, L) and (M^n, L^*)

The tangent vector space M_x^n to M^n at every point x is regarded as n-dimensional Riemannian space (M_x^n, g_x) with Riemannian metric $g_x = g_{ij}(x, y) dy^i dy^j$. Thus the component C_{jk}^i of Cartan's C-tensor are the Christoffel symbols associated with g_x , i.e.

$$C_{jk}^i = \frac{1}{2} g^{ih} (\partial_k g_{jh} + \partial_j g_{hk} + \partial_h g_{jk}).$$

Hence C_{jk}^i defines the Riemannian connection on M_x^n . It is observed from the definition if S_{hijk} that the curvature tensor of the Riemannian space (M_x^n, g_x) at a point x . The space (M_x^n, g_x) equipped with such a Riemannian connection will be called the tangent Riemannian space.

In the theory of Riemannian space, we know that any n-dimensional Riemannian space V^n , can be imbedded isometrically in a Euclidean space of dimension $\frac{n(n-1)}{2}$. If $n+r$ is the lowest dimension of the Euclidean space in which V^n is imbedded isometrically then the integer r is called imbedding class number of V^n . The fundamental theorem of isometric imbedding [1] states that the tangent Riemannian n-space (M_x^n, g_x) is locally imbedded isometrically in an Euclidean $n+r$ space if and only if there exist r numbers, and $\lambda = \pm 1$, r symmetric tensor $H_{(P)ij}$ and $\frac{r(r-1)}{2}$ covariant vector fields $H_{(PQ)i} = H_{(QP)i}$, $Q = 1, 2, 3, \dots, r$ satisfying the Gauss equations,

$$S_{hijk} = \text{Sigma} \lambda_{(P)} \{H_{(P)hj} H_{(P)ik} - H_{(P)hk} H_{(P)ij}\},$$

where summation is given over P .

The Codazzi equations

$$H_{(P)ij}|_k - H_{(P)ik}|_j = \Sigma \lambda_{(Q)} \{H_{(Q)ij} H_{(QP)k} - H_{(Q)ik} H_{(QP)j}\},$$

where summation is given over Q and Ricci-Kuhne equations

$$\begin{aligned} & H_{(PQ)i}|_j - H_{(PQ)j}|_i + \Sigma \lambda_{(R)} \{H_{(RP)i} H_{(RQ)j} \\ & - H_{(RP)j} H_{(PQ)i}\} + g^{hk} \{H_{(P)hi} H_{(Q)kj} - H_{(P)hj} H_{(Q)ki}\} = 0. \end{aligned}$$

For a special case when (M_x^n, g_x) is of imbedding class 1, the above equations reduce to

$$S_{hijk} = \lambda(H_{hj}H_{ik} - H_{hk}H_{ij}), \quad (4.1)$$

$$H_{ij|k} - H_{ik|j} = 0. \quad (4.2)$$

Since $S_{hijk}y^k = 0$, from (3.21), we have

$$H_{hj}H_{i0} - H_{h0}H_{ij} = 0$$

contracting above equation by y^i , we have

$$H_{hj}H_{00} - H_{h0}H_{0j} = 0,$$

which implies that $H_{0j} = 0$ or $H_{ij} = H_{00}^{-1}H_{h0}H_{0j}$. In the latter case we get $S_{hijk} = 0$. In the theory of spaces of imbedding class 1, [17] introduced the concept of type number t , which is the rank of matrix $\|H_{ij}\|$ provided to the rank is more than 1. If the rank is 0 or 1, then S vanishes. Therefore if (M_x^n, g_x) is of imbedding class 1, the second fundamental tensor H_{ij} satisfies $H_{ij}y^j = 0$ and thus the type number t is less than n .

Again by virtue of Lemma 2.3 and equation (4.1), we get

$$H_{hj}H_{ik} - H_{hk}H_{ij}b^h = 0.$$

From this equation we have

$$H_{hj}b^hb^jH_{ik} - H_{hk}b^hH_{ij}b^j = 0.$$

This gives

$$H_{hk}b^h = 0, \quad \text{or} \quad H_{ik} = \frac{H_{hk}b^hH_{ij}b^j}{H_{hj}b^hb^j}.$$

In the latter case $S_{hijk} = 0$. Thus for an imbedding class 1, $H_{hk}b^k = 0$. Now we shall put

$$H_{(1)ij}^* = \sqrt{\sigma}H_{ij}, \quad \varepsilon_1^* = \varepsilon, \quad (4.3)$$

$$H_{(2)ij}^* = A_{ij}, \quad \varepsilon_2^* = -1, \quad 4.4$$

$$H_{(3)ij}^* = B_{ij}, \quad \varepsilon_3^* = 1, \quad 4.5$$

then from (3.15) and (4.1), we get

$$S_{hijk}^* = \Sigma \lambda_P^* \{H_{(P)hj}^* H_{(P)ik}^* - H_{(P)hh}^* H_{(P)ij}^*\},$$

where summation is varies from $P = 1, 2, 3$. Thus the above equation is noting but Gauss equation of (M_x^n, g_x^*) .

Now we put

$$H_{(21)i}^* = -H_{(12)i}^* = 0, \quad (4.6)$$

$$H_{(31)i}^* = -H_{(13)i}^* = 0, \quad (4.7)$$

$$H_{(32)i}^* = -H_{(23)i}^* = \frac{1}{L}l_i \quad (4.8)$$

and using (4.2), (4.3), (3.3), Lemma 2.1 and the fact that $H_{i0} = 0$, we get

$$H_{(1)ij|k}^* - H_{(1)ik|j}^* = 0. \quad (4.9)$$

Again in view of (4.4), (4.5), (4.6), (4.7) and (4.8), equations (3.19) and (3.20) reduce to

$$H_{(2)ij|k}^* - H_{(2)ik|j}^* = \Sigma \lambda_Q^* \{H_{(Q)ij}^* H_{(Q2)k}^* - H_{(Q)ik}^* H_{(Q2)j}^*\}, \quad 4.10$$

$$H_{(3)ij|k}^* - H_{(3)ik|j}^* = \Sigma \lambda_Q^* \{H_{(Q)ij}^* H_{(Q3)k}^* - H_{(Q)ik}^* H_{(Q3)j}^*\}, \quad 4.11$$

where summation is varies from $Q = 1, 2, 3$.

The equations (4.9), (4.10) and (4.11) are the Codazzi equations of (M_x^n, g_x^*) . Now we have to verify Ricci-Kuhne equations, we have from (3.10),

$$l_i|_j = L^{-1}h_{ij+L^{*-1}}[\{\rho + (2L^*)^{-1}(v^2 - \frac{\beta^2}{L^2})\}h_{ij} + L^{*-1}m_i m_j]$$

from which we get $l_i|_j - l_j|_i = 0$. Hence from (4.10), we get

$$H_{(32)i|j}^* - H_{(23)j|i}^* = 0,$$

which are the Ricci-Kuhne equations of (M_x^n, g_x^*) as

$$M_{(12)}^* - M_{(21)}^* = 0, \quad \text{and} \quad M_{(13)}^* - M_{(31)}^* = 0.$$

Thus from above we have

Theorem 4.1 *Let $F^{*n} = (M^n, L^*)$ be an n -dimensional Finsler space obtained from the h-Randers change of the Finsler space $F^n = (M^n, L)$, then if the tangent Riemannian n -space (M_x^n, g_x) to (M^n, L) is of imbedding class 1, then the tangent Riemannian n -space (M_x^n, g_x) to (M^n, L^*) is at most of imbedding class 3.*

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